

The genus *Pelycidion* (Mollusca: Archaegastropoda) in West Africa

El género *Pelycidion* (Mollusca: Archaegastropoda) en África occidental

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Recibido el 2-V-2002. Aceptado el 20-XII-2002

ABSTRACT

West African shells of the genus *Pelycidion* (family Pelycidiidae Ponder and Hall, 1983) are studied, photographed and compared; the conclusion reached is that only one variable species is present in this area. Some characteristics of the shell of this species are illustrated.

RESUMEN

Las conchas de África Occidental pertenecientes al género *Pelycidion* (familia Pelycidiidae Ponder and Hall, 1983) son estudiadas, fotografiadas y comparadas, llegándose a la conclusión de que, en esta área, sólo existe una especie morfológicamente muy variable. Se muestran y comentan algunos caracteres de la concha.

KEY WORDS: *Pelycidion*, West Africa, shell characters.

PALABRAS CLAVE: *Pelycidion*, África occidental, caracteres de la concha.

INTRODUCTION

FOLIN AND PÉRIER (1873) described from Hong-Kong and Senegal the first known species of the family Pelycidiidae Ponder and Hall, 1983, which was named *Pelycidion venustulum* Fischer.

PONDER AND HALL (1983) proposed the family name Pelycidiidae, with *Pelycidion venustulum* as its type species; the type locality is restricted to Senegal. This work also mentions the generic synonyms and lists the previously known species of this genus, illustrating most of them.

The position of this family in this last work is not clear but it is tentatively placed in Archaegastropoda. Later,

BOUCHET AND LE RENARD (1998) placed it near Pickworthiidae; even the possibility that it may be a synonym of this family is mentioned (as a personal communication from W. F. Ponder). OKUTANI (2000) places the family Pelycidionidae (sic!) between the families Pickworthiidae and Cingulopsidae.

Two species from West Africa are mentioned in these works:

-*Pelycidion venustulum*, represented in PONDER AND HALL (1983, figs. 1F and 1G) showing shells from Mauritania.

-*Pelycidion* sp., represented in PONDER AND HALL (1983, figs. 1E and 3B-3E) showing shells from Dahomey.

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MATERIAL AND METHODS

In sediment samples dredged by the authors in Ghana, several shells of this genus were found. This material was noted to be complementary with more shells from Senegal (J. Pelorce coll.) and Angola (F. Fernandes coll.). In the present work, the authors have made comparison of the shell characteristics (protoconch, size, sculpture of the last

whorl and microsculpture) of all the material obtained, comparing it with those in the above-mentioned literature. All the material studied is in collection of the first author (CER).

Abbreviations:

s shell
f fragment
j juvenile

RESULTS

Genus *Pelycidion* Fischer in Folin and Périer, 1873

Type species: *Pelycidion venustum* Fischer, 1873. For monotypy.
For synonyms and general characters see PONDER AND HALL (1983).

Pelycidion venustum Fischer, 1873

Pelycidion venustum Fischer, in Folin and Périer, 1873. *Les fonds de la mer.*: 182.

Type material: Untraceable.

Material examined: Senegal: 1 specimen, 2 s, 1 f, Petit Thouriba, Dakar, 35 m ; 2 s, Grand Thiouriba, Dakar, 33 m ; 18 s, Madeleines, Dakar, 6-14 m ; 38 s, Madeleines, Dakar, 18 m ; 23 s, Madeleines, Dakar, 6-14 m ; 15 s, Cap Vert, Epave "Tacoma", 15 m ; 15 s, Tiwa, Dakar, 35 m . Ghana: 3 s, Miamia, 12 m ; 31 s, 6 j, 10 f, Miamia, 35-40 m ; 14 s, Miamia, 45-50 m ; 34 s, 5 f, Cape Three Points, 35-65 m. Angola: 2 s, Corimba, Luanda, 20 m ; 1 s, off Luanda, 60-100 m ; 1 s, Namibe, 25 m .

Description: Shell (Figs. 1-11) minute, elongate-pupoid, relatively solid, whitish or cream-coloured. Protoconch (Figs. 12-17) brownish in fresh shells, with about 2 whorls, with a smooth beginning of almost 1 whorl; the subsequent part exhibits an evident sculpture; in the subsutural area, this is formed at the beginning by an oblique reticulation and at the end by axial ribs; in the middle of the whorl, there are fine spiral threads, being adapically stronger. At the end of the protoconch, there is a pronounced subsutural sinus. The teleoconch has between $3\frac{1}{2}$ – $4\frac{1}{2}$ whorls which increase in size gradually being hardly convex or almost flat. Suture impressed. The last whorl is large, representing almost $\frac{1}{2}$ of the total height of the shell. Some shells indicate a last whorl uniformly curved towards the periphery, while others show a strong

spiral cord which begins at the end of the suture and forms a peripheral keel. The aperture is circular or subcircular and weakly thickened externally towards the apical part. Peristome simple.

The microsculpture (Figs. 18-23) is highly variable; sometimes, the shell appears to be smooth and only under magnification the regular spiral striae, which are formed by one or two rows of small indentations separated by larger interspaces, can be observed. In other cases, these rows of pits are separated by similar interspaces and appear as a continuous sculpture. In some shells, stronger striae appear and the pits or indentations may or may not be visible. Even in this last case, one shell we observed exhibits on the first whorls the classical pitted sculpture and on the last whorl this other striated sculpture.

Figures 1-11. Shells of *P. venustulum*. 1: 1.4 mm, Madeleines, Senegal; 2-4: 1.3, 1.3 and 1.3 mm, off Luanda, 60-120 m, Angola; 5-11: 1.8, 1.3, 1.4, 1.1, 1.4, 1.1 and 1.3 mm, Miamia, Ghana.
 Figuras 1-11. Conchas de *P. venustulum*. 1: 1,4 mm, Madeleines, Senegal; 2-4: 1,3, 1,3 y 1,3 mm, fuera de Luanda, 60-120 m, Angola; 5-11: 1,8, 1,3, 1,4, 1,1, 1,4, 1,1 y 1,3 mm, Miamia, Ghana.

Figures 12-17. Protoconchs of *P. venustulum*. 12: Madeleines, Dakar, Senegal, 35 m; 13: off Luanda, Angola, 60-100 m; 14-16: Miamia, Ghana, 20-65 m; 17: La Tacoma, Dakar, Senegal, 15 m.

Figuras 12-17. Protoconchas de P. venustulum. 12: Madeleines, Dakar, Senegal, 35 m; 13: fuera de Luanda, Angola, 60-100 m; 14-16: Miamia, Ghana, 20-65 m; 17: La Tacoma, Dakar, Senegal, 15 m.

Figures 18-23. Microsculpture from shells of *P. venustum*. 18: Senegal; 19, 20: Angola; 21-23. Ghana.

Figuras 18-23. Microescultura de conchas de P. venustum. 18: Senegal; 19, 20: Angola; 21-23. Ghana.

Dimensions: The shell height is variable, the smallest shells of our material measured 1.0 mm, and the largest 1.8 mm; material of both sizes was collected in the same place.

Operculum (Fig. 24) is multispiral; it was examined in only one specimen of *Pelycidion* from Dakar, with the operculum visible at the aperture and the soft parts dry into.

Radula (Figs. 25, 26) which has the same appearance to that showed in PONDER AND HALL (1083) from a species of West America.

Distribution: The species is known from Mauritania (mentioned in PONDER AND HALL, 1983) and Senegal (type locality) up to Angola.

Discussion: After the examination of the material from several countries and

Figures 24-26. *P. venustulum*, Dakar, Senegal. 24: Operculum; 25, 26: radula.
Figuras 24-26. *P. venustulum*, Dakar, Senegal. 24: Opérculo; 25, 26: rádula.

the graphic material shown in PONDER AND HALL (1983) we have found that the morphology of this species is very variable and there are intergradation between the different sized shells as well as in the sculpture of the last whorl and microsculpture. For these reasons we conclude that only one species exists on the West African coast which we illustrate in this work from several aspects to show the variability.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Our thanks to J. Pelorce for the loan of material; to Jesús Méndez of the CACTI of the University of Vigo for the SEM photographs; also to the PARSYST project for our estancia in the MNHN of Paris, and the bibliographic information.

This work has been partially supported by a grant of XUNTA DE GALICIA PGIDTOOPXI30121PR.

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